

RAIL TRACK ELECTRIFICATION IN CONNECTIVITY OF NORTH-EAST INDIA WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO ASSAM

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Abstract:

Indian Railways has taken various steps to prioritize investment in important areas. Indian Railways seeing stiff competition from other modes of transportation, the Government of India is initiating various transformative measures to keep railways on track. These measures are focusing on prioritizing investment in important areas like Dedicated Freight Corridors, high speed rail, high capacity rolling stock, last mile rail linkage, port connectivity and attracting private and foreign investment. It is holds that the tremendous prospects in the short, medium and long term as it undergoes rapid modernization. In the upgrading railway infrastructure has become a core focus for the Government. Electrification of railway route from Katihar to Raninagar Jalpaiguri and from Maldah Town to Kumedpur sections had been in an advanced stage. The project for electrification from Raninagar Jalpaiguri to New Bongaigaon and then from New Bongaigaon to Guwahati was entrusted with Rail Vikash Nigam Limited , a Mini Ratna Public Sector Undertaking under Ministry of Railways, in 2014 and 2015 respectively in Assam. The Rail Vikash Nigam Limited will execute the project on turnkey basis. Under the project 382 route km and 687 track km of railway lines will be electrified. Completion of the project will ensure that Guwahati will have a seamless electrified route to cities like Kolkata and New Delhi and eliminate the need for changing locomotives from electric to diesel and vice versa. This will also ensure reduction of journey time and possibility of increasing speed of trains. Northeast Frontier Railway after taking a quantum leap by eliminating all unmanned level crossings has now embarked for complete railway track electrification till Guwahati targeted to be completed by 2020 and in the rest of the Northeast states by 2022 with the Northeast Frontier Railways (NFR) setting the same target.

Key Words: Electrification, Railways, Connectivity, North Eastern Region & Assam

1. Introduction

The North East region comprises eight states- Arunachal Pradesh, Manipur, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Nagaland, Sikkim, Tripura and Assam. The Northeast is the home to 4 percent of the national population, while Assam accounts for 68 percent of the population, occupies about 8 percent of India's total geographical area and is strategically important with over 5,300 km of international borders has 96 percent of its boundaries surrounded by – China, Nepal, and Bhutan in the North, Bangladesh in the South-West and Myanmar in the East. In the past history, the mighty Himalayas in the North always kept India physically aloof from China. The North-East State of India share International borders which the State-wise length of International Border of the North-Eastern Region they share total – Arunachal Pradesh 1,817km, Assam 530km, Manipur 398, Meghalaya 443, Mizoram 828, Nagaland 215, Sikkim 350 and Tripura 856. Among them the Arunachal Pradesh longest International border share with China total 1,080km, second position Tripura share 856km with Bangladesh and in third position Mizoram has 510 international border lines with Myanmar.

Indian Railway is the fourth largest in the world after Russia, the U.S.A. and Canada. In a vast country like India, it has brought the people of the farthest corners of the country closer to one another. The upgrading of the rail network in the North Eastern Region has received significant attention of the Ministry of Railways. Capacity has been augmented manifold leading to introduction a large number of long distance passenger carrying trains and removal or reduction of transshipment activities which hitherto has been the single biggest bottleneck in smooth movement of traffic. Historically, undivided Bengal and the North-Eastern region were and integrated market with active roads, railway tracks and waterways crisscrossing the region. Global trade was conducted through the sea route, network of inland waterways, and land transportation through road and railways. In fact, the network between Dibrugarh and Chittagong was one of the earliest railway projects in India implemented by the British commenced in 1884. By 1950, India reconnected Assam to the rest of the country's rail network by building a more than 200-km metre-gauge rail link through the Siliguri corner. The lack of connectivity and infrastructure the North Eastern Region has faced low trade activity in the region. 95 percent of India's exports to neighbouring states of Bangladesh, Bhutan and Myanmar are from other than North East India. This is also despite that fact that the region is the natural gateway for India to the East Asian, South Asian and South Asian Economies. There is on-going major rail construction programme in the North Eastern

Region. These projects are now on a firm footing with accelerated funding provided to North Eastern Region projects. This should be continued to achieve the vision of connecting all the states capitals by 2020.

The Northeast Frontier Railway is one of the 17 railway zones India, headquartered in Maligaon, Guwahati in the state of Assam, is it responsible for rail operations in the entire Northeast and parts of West Bengal and Bihar. In 1881, railway first came to Assam when Assam Railway and Trading Company set up metre gauge track. The 65 km long metre gauge line from Dibrugarh to Margherita was constructed mainly for transportation of tea and coal. This company later started the first passenger train in Assam by the name of 'Dibru Sadiya Railway'. The North Eastern Railway was formed on 14 April 1952 by amalgamating two railway systems – the Assam Railway and Oudh and Tirhut Railway. Later, it was bifurcated into two railway zones on 15 January 1958, the North Eastern Railway and the Northeast Frontier Railway to better serve the needs of the North Eastern States.

2. Review of Literature:

Ram Chandra Acharya (2000) the first railway in the world was the Stockton & Darlington in the UK, which was opened in 1825. Railways reached France in 1829, the USA in 1830, Germany in 1835, Italy and the Netherlands in 1839, and Spain in 1848. Railways came relatively late to India when the first of 21 miles (33.6 km) was opened from Boribunder to Thane in 1853. The grand occasion was marked by a 21 – gun salute and even the Governor's band was in attendance when 14 railway carriages carrying 400 guests left Boribunder at 15:30 and arrived at Thane 16:45. By the time of independence in 1947, the British had built a railway network of more than 58,000 km primarily for developing the hinterlands and transporting agriculture produce, minerals, and troops to suppress uprisings. Rather surprisingly, private enterprise played the leading role in railway construction during the early 19th century. Since the colonial government guaranteed a 5 percent return on investment, growth was phenomenal in the early stages.

Anand Kumar Choudhary & Dr. Srinivas Rao (2018) Transportation is important part of people which directly and indirectly connected with people. It enables trade between people which is essential for the development of Civilisation. Transportation is the backbone of any economic, culture, social and industrial development of any country. Transportation is the movement of human, animal and goods from one location to another. Rail transportation is where trains along a set of two parallel steel rails, known as a railway or railroad. Passenger transport may be public where provide fixed scheduled service. Freight transport has become focused on containerization; bulk transport is used for large volumes of durable item. Rail transport is a means of transferring of passenger and goods on wheeled running on rail, also known as tracks, tracks usually consist of steel rail, installed on ties (sleepers) and ballast. Railway transport is capable of high level of passenger and goods utilization and energy efficiency but is often less flexible and more capital intensive than road transport when tower traffic level are considered.

3. Objectives of the Study:

The major objectives of the study are as follows:

- To focus the new railways lines connecting the neighbouring countries of India is considering as essential to improve transportation in the North Eastern Region.
- To analyse the Electrification of Rail Tract including in Assam.
- To understand the importance of Rail Electrification in Assam.
- To concentrates of Study on Indian Railways, electrification is cheaper source of energy and electric rolling stock is also capable of regeneration process.

4. Materials and Methods:

For the purpose of the study of "Rail Track Electrification in Connectivity of North-East India with special reference to Assam", an analytical study follows the descriptive method. In this study data have been collected by using secondary sources. Secondary data and information have been collected from different published books, journals, internet sources, published research papers and articles, newspapers.

5. History of World Railway:

The earliest recorded illustration of railway dates back to 1320, showing a small wooden mine trolley running in recessed stone guides, possibly originating in ancient Greece. The Railway, in its true sense, emerged in the early seventeenth century when the first wooden tracks were laid at Wallaton, England, in 1604 to be used for running of horse-drawn carriage. It was only in February 1804, a good two centuries later, that Richard Trevithick, an engineer, ran the world's first steam engine successfully on rails. The locomotive, with its single vertical cylinder, 8-foot flywheel and long piston rod, managed to haul ten tones of iron, seventy passengers and five wagons from the ironworks at Penydarren to the Merthyr-Cardiff Canal. This was, however, a train run and cannot be termed as first Railway passenger service train. In 1821, Edward Pease, a wool merchant, during his travels of buying and selling wool, felt that a railroad with wagons drawn by horses to carry coal from the collieries of West Durham to the port of Stockton would be of great help. The same year, Pease and a group of businessmen formed the Stockton & Darlington Railroad company. However, Nicolas Wood, the Manager of Killingworth Colliery and his engineer George Stephenson, had a better idea. They met Pease and suggested that he should consider building a locomotive railway instead. And after some thought Pease did agree. The

Stockton & Darlington Railroad was opened on 27 September, 1825. The engine, built by George Stephenson, pulled 36 wagons, including twelve wagons of coal and flour, six of guests and fourteen wagons full of workmen. This has been recorded as the first passengers train in the world. But this was disputed and some claim the Liverpool-Manchester Railway of 1825 as the first passengers' railway. However, disputes apart, railway communications gained popularity in the 1830s and since then there has been no backward journey. Railways reached France in 1829, the USA in 1830, Germany in 1835, Italy and the Netherlands in 1839, and Spain in 1848. The world's first underground railway the Metropolitan Railway (part of the London Underground), opened in 1863. In the 1880, electrified train were introduced, leading to electrifications of tramway starting during the 1940s the non electrified railway in most countries had their steam locomotive replaced by diesel electric locomotives the process being almost complete by the 2000. During the 1960, electrified high-speed railway systems were introduced in Japan and later in some other countries. Many countries are in process of replacing diesel locomotives with electric locomotives.

6. History of Indian Railway:

In 1846, there was a major failure of cotton crop in America. Following this, textile merchants at Manchester and Glasgow in Great Britain had to seek alternative markets. It was then that traders in the UK turned their attention on the cotton crop in India, one of Britain colonies then, rich in cotton crop. However, cotton was produced in various parts of the Indian sub-continent and it took days to bring it to the nearest part to transport it to England through ships, the only major means of international communication then. The British then had to build a link from the hinterland to India's major ports for quicker transport of cotton and other goods as demand soared. This expedited matters for the British to introduce a railway in India. The British also felt that organisation the growing and dispersing the growing native population faster deployment of troops could be better handle by a railway. As early as 1843, Lord Dalhousie had first conceived the possibility of opening up of India by means of railway communication. He had proposed to link the three ports of Bombay, Calcutta and Madras by a railway. The same year he sent George T. Clarke, an engineer, to Bombay to assess the possibility. A few years later in 1845, a strong lobby in Bombay supporting railway communication formed a body called the Bombay Great Eastern Railway. As matters started to gain momentum, the Bombay Great Eastern Railway locally prepared plans for constructing a railway line from Bombay to the Deccan. But the British already had a concrete plan in their minds and soon things began to take shape. The earliest proposal for laying railways in India was made some time around in the 1830s. Inspired by the railway mania in England, some eminent citizens in Madras had proposed the idea of a railway but plans remained on paper and the project did not see the light of the day then. Conditions in India were quite different those in Britain. Many British and Indians, who had better understanding about India's topography and geography, opposed the construction of railways as a "premature and expensive undertaking" and a "hazardous and dangerous venture". Certain opponents doubted the feasibility of introduction of railways in India citing poverty, extreme climate with torrential rains, violent storms, high mountains, sandy deserts and dense forests. But the process of building a railway network that would one day not only captivate that nation but the whole world had already begun.

The first train steamed off in the country in 1853 from Bombay (Boribunder/Boree Bunder) to Thane, covering a distance of 33.6 km. The grand occasion was marked by a 21 – gun salute and even the Governor's band was in attendance when 14 railway carriages carrying 400 guests left Bombay (Boribunder/Boree Bunder) at 15:30 and arrived at Thane 16:45. By the time of independence in 1947, the British had built a railway network of more than 58,000 km primarily for developing the hinterlands and transporting agriculture produce, minerals, and troops to suppress uprisings. Rather surprisingly, private enterprise played the leading role in railway construction during the early 19th century. Since the colonial government guaranteed a 5 percent return on investment, growth was phenomenal in the early stages.

7. Zones of Indian Railways in 1950 and 1958:

The Railway Board in 1950 decided for the regrouping of the Indian Railway into six Zonal system, namely, the Northern, the North Eastern, the Southern, the Central, the Eastern and the Western Railways. The unequal distributions of workload on some of the railways have led further bifurcation of zones. The Eastern Railway was split into two zones, namely, Eastern Railway and South Eastern Railway. Similarly, North Eastern Zone was also split into the North Eastern Railway and the North Eastern Frontier Railway. Thus, by the year 1958, there were eight zones in the Indian Railways.

8. Measures of Indian Railway:

Indian Railways have taken several measures to improve their efficiency and usefulness to the public:

- Considering increase in railway running track
- Increase in electrification of busy trunk routes
- Conversion of metre gauge railway lines into broad gauge
- Introducing several types of fast and superfast passenger trains
- Running fast goods and special foodgrain trains
- Providing better facilities for reservation and other customer care services, including reservation through internet.

9. Rail Tracks of North-East States:

The railways entered the remote areas of Eastern region relatively earlier than the more accessible regions of British India. Assam Railway and Trading Company Commission a 65-km meter gauge track from Dibrugarh to Margherita in 1881. Commercial interest of the East India Company in trading of tea and coal drove the technological upgradation in transportation. Discovery of petroleum catalyzed the growth, and around 1947, just before Independence, the whole North- Eastern Region, which included the erstwhile East Bengal, now Bangladesh, was buzzing with robust railways connectivity to the mainland as well as with the deep port Chittagong the fulcrum of all international trade for the region.

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In 1958, a new railway line zone, viz. Northeast Frontier Railway was carved out of the North Eastern Railway with headquarters at Maligaon, Guwahati. There are presently five divisions which serve these eight North Eastern states, that is, Katihar, Alipurduar, Rangia, Lumding and Tinsukia. Today NF Railway directly or indirectly serves all the eight North Eastern states besides West Bengal and Bihar. The NF Railway has become the lifeline of the North Eastern Region transporting essential goods all over the region. It moves coal and petroleum products from the rest of India. NF Railway also serves as a rail head for the landlocked Himalayan countries of Nepal and Bhutan and provides interchange facilities with Bangladesh.

Railways are the best mode of mass transportation in the country. However, in the hilly terrains of the North-East it is difficult and expensive to setup rail networks. This account for the absence or nominal presence of railways lines in hilly states like Arunachal Pradesh, Manipur, Meghalaya and Mizoram. Even in Nagaland and Tripura the railway route has been setup in the plain area of the region.

In the Rail Budget 2012-13, a survey for railway electrification project has been sanctioned for Assam. It is envisaged bringing the Northern Banks of the Brahmaputra River under rail connectivity. Tripura is another state in the North-East Region where development of railway infrastructure is picking up well. From 2000 to 2010, the length of railway route in Tripura has increased from 41 km to 152 km. There are three major railway stations located in Dharmanagar, Agartala and Kumarghat. The government has proposed a 14km metre gauge railway line between Agartala (Tripura) and Akhaura (Bangladesh). In addition, there is a railway-linked to develop between Agartala and Sabroom covering 110km. In Arunachal Pradesh the nearest railway station in located at Harmoti in Assam 33km from Itanagar. The major functional rail head linking Manipur with the rest of India is at Dimapur (Nagaland), 215 km away from Imphal. However, a railway line from Jiribam, on the border of Manipur-Assam is under construction as a national priority project. New railway lines on Azra-Byrnihat, Dudnoi-Mehendipather and Byrnihat-Shillong routes in Meghalaya are important construction for the people of the North-East states. The construction of the extension of a vital broad gauge rail link between Bhairabi rail terminus on the Mizoram-Assam border and Sairang, a village 20 km west of Aizwal, is in progress. In Sikkim rail connectivity is being created between Rangpo and Siliguri in West Bengal. A railway track is also to be laid for connecting Agartala with Akhaura in Bangladesh. The following map shows the rail road connectivity in all the capital of the North Eastern India States.

9.1 Objectives of Rail Project, Ministry of Railway in North Eastern Region:

The major objectives to strengthen and expand the railway infrastructure by the Ministry of Railways in North Eastern Region are presently as follows:

- Connectivity to all State Capitals
- Conversion to unigauge- regionwide broadgauge network
- Augmentation of network capacity for handling growth of traffic in future
- Expansion of network to unconnected areas of the region
- Improving trade and connectivity with neighbouring countries
- Strengthening international borders.

9.2 New Phases of Development Northeastern Frontier Railway:

In order to provide focused attention to asset creation in the North Eastern Region, planning should be carried out in two phases, that is, Phase I (Upto 2020) and Phase II (2020- 2030)

Phase I (Upto 2020):

The Railways' shelf of projects is full to the brim for works upto 2020. Determined and planned efforts are imperative to achieve rail connectivity to all the capitals by 2020. All the remaining alignments to each of the capitals towns which expected to works get completed by 2020. At present, only Guwahati and Agartala are connected by rail.

Arunachal Pradesh: Itanagar has to be joined to the Rangia-Murkongselek route (which is under gauge conversion) at Harmuti. It is a sanctioned work upto Naharlagun which will act as a terminal for Itanagar.

Manipur: The track from Jiribam to Tupul will get commissioned and the extension from Tupul to Imphal has sanctioned.

Mizoram: Aizwal the capital of Mizoram is to be connected to Badarpur on existing alignment via Bhairabi. Bhairabi to Sairang and Sairang to Aizwal is a sectioned.

Meghalaya: Shillong is to be linked to Tetelia on the existing rail route but at present only Tetelia by Byrnihat route is under construction. Byrnihat to Shillong portion has been sanctioned.

Nagaland: at present work is sanctioned from Dimapur to Zubza and extension to Kohima.

Sikkim: Sivok to Rangpo is sanctioned and is extension to be Rangpo to Gangtok. And it is also rail connectivity to expedited upto Nathu La.

Argumentation of Network Capacity:

The development of the rail network in the rail area is likely to increase the freight and passenger traffic and therefore augmentation of the network capacity will be needed. At present, the route from New Jalpaiguri to Lumding has doubled line in parts. With passenger and freight traffic likely to go up considerably in the future, the entire stretch from New Jalpaiguri to Guwahati will need to be doubled. The following routes are expected to be strengthened in due course.

Doubling Lines:

- Doubling of New Jalpaiguri to New Alipurduar route
- Doubling of New Bongaigaon to Guwahati route and doubling Guwahati to Lumding route. This route is to common portion which serves traffic going to Dibrugarh side and towards Silchar. To avoid congestion, this route needs to be doubled. A part of the route between Guwahati and Digaru has already been completed and commissioned.

Phase II (2020-2032):

The projects being undertaken in Phase I will provide excellent inter-regional and intra-regional connectivity. Yet, the following two actions will further catalyse trade, commerce, tourism in the region.

Multi-Modal Hubs:

Badarpur and Dhubri are two locations which are eminently suitable for development as multi-modal hubs, particularly for the following reasons:

- Badarpur is a railway junction situated very close to Silchar. Indian Railways owns large tracks of land on which a suitable yard can be built to serve the needs of a multi-modal rail terminal handling containers of various sizes. The Barak river flows close by, where and Inland waterways port terminal can be planned. A National Highway passed through the town. Silchar nearly 18 km away has an operational airport.
- Dhubri is another such location. Located in close proximity to the Bangladesh border, it is situated on the Banks of the mighty Brahmaputra where the Inland Waterway Authority is already in the process of developing of an Inland port. Dhubri is already on the railway map and NH-31 passes through the town. An airport at Rupsi 24 km away is also coming up by 2020.

It is hence, proposed that Badarpur and Dhubri should be developed as multi-modal hubs in the North East Region, where all the four modes of transport- rail, road, air and waterways-coverage. These hubs are also strategically so well placed-both geographically and demographically that they may be amenable to be developed through PPP mode.

New Line from Dhubri to Silchar via Shillong:

It is suggested that a new line through Meghalaya connecting Dhubri to Silchar via Tura-Shillong should be surveyed and taken up as an alternate route for Badarpur-Silchar and beyond. This is new alignment will link the entry point of Dhubri on the Indo-Bangladesh border to Meghalaya and Southern Assam. It would create a link between the two proposed multi-modal hubs at Dhubri and Badarpur 8km near Silchar. At Shillong, it will connect also will the new sanctioned line to Byrnihat in Meghalaya on the Guwahati-Shillong road providing another alternate connection.

Trans-Border Connectivity:

New line between Imphal-Moreh-Mandalay:

By 2020, the railway should arrive in Imphal. In Phase II, this alignment should be extended to Mandalaya in Myanmar via Moreh-Tamu which is emerging as India's gateway on the land route to South East Asia. With the doors of democracy having opened in Myanmar, trade and commerce between India and Myanmar is bound to escalate. A helpful infrastructure will only galvanise this progress. Further, this is bound to give a fillip to the Look East Policy / Act East Policy. However, it is suggested that this connectivity should be provided on broad gauge upto Mandalay to ensure seamless movement across borders.

New Rail Link from Sittwe (Myanmar):

India has invested heavily in developing Sittwe port in Myanmar in the Rakhine region. The transportation of goods via this port is at present planned by road and inland waterways. Kaladan Multi-Modal Project has been undertaken to connect Sittwe port to India which includes development of waterways on Kaladan River and also a road connecting Sittwe port to Mizoram. However, it is felt that without proper rail

connectivity, the potential of a major port cannot be exploited fully. It is hence suggested that the Indian government should plan for a rail link BG from Sittwe port to Aizwal in consultation with the Myanmar government. This alignment can be taking up further north from Aizwal to Imphal to Kohima to Tirap on the existing rail route to Tinsukhia. This rail link, if constructed, will generate many alternate rail routes for the whole region, thereby precluding any possibility of complete blockage of one state by rogue group in a neighbouring state. If the Imphal-Moreh-Mandalay line also comes up, it will provide a handy connectivity to every state to take on international trade. A direct rail link between Aizwal and Agartala will convert the whole alignment as a 'garland' on the neck of the North East Region adorning its bodypolitics.

Imphal as New Rail Hub (National & International):

Imphal can become a potential rail hub in future through possible project extensions in the following:

Present Proposal: Jiribam-Tupul-Imphal (National Project)

- Eastward extension: Imphal-Moreh-Mandalay
- Northward Extension: Imphal-Kohima-via Northern Nagaland-Tirap (Arunachal Pradesh)
- Southern extension: line coming from Paletwa (on the Kadalan Multi-Modal route)-Indo-Myanmar border-Lawngtlai-Aizwal Churachandpur-Imphal.

It is proposed that Imphal will become a hub for railway connectivity with Myanmar from two sides and also get Nagaland and Arunachal Pradesh.

10. Indian Railways Electric Traction:

Electric traction is a more environment friendly option. By using electric traction over diesel traction, the nation reduces the use of fossil fuel, reduces import of petroleum and reduces its carbon footprints. For Indian Railways, electrification is cheaper source of energy and electric rolling stock is also capable of regeneration process. The use of rail electrification increase in speed, ease of operation and better economic viability of the operations are the main positive aspects of using electric traction. Over the years, Indian Railway has undertaken the work of electrification of various routes or section. The Vision 2020 document stated that 33,000 Route Kilo Miters (RKMs) would be electrified by March 2020. By 31 March 2016, total 27,999 Route Kilo Miters (RKMs) out of 58,825 Route Kilo Miters (RKMs) have been electrified, 12,710 Route Kilo Miters (RKMs) have been included in the works programme and the remaining 18,116 Route Kilo Miters (RKMs) were yet to be sanctioned. In August 2016, the target was revised by Railway Board to cover 24,427 Route Kilo Miters (RKMs) under electrified routes by 31 March 2021, including 12,710 Route Kilo Miters (RKMs) in progress and 11,717 Route Kilo Miters (RKMs) (out of 18,116 Route Kilo Miters (RKMs)) of missing links between already electrification sections.

The responsibility to carry out Railway Electrification was entrusted to a specialized agency of the Indian Railway, that is, Central Organisation for Railway Electrification (CORE), which was set up in 1979 at Allahabad. Projects are also entrusted to Rail Vikas Nigam Limited (RVNL), a Railway Public Sector Undertaking on nomination basis. Railway Board has also allocated some projects to Zonal Railways (Central Railway, Western Railway and East Coast Railway). Railway Board has also decided to assign Railway Electrification projects to Indian Railway Construction organisation (IRCON), Rail India Technical and Economic Services Limited (RITES) (Railways' PSUs) and power Grid Corporation of India Limited (PGCIL) (PSU under the Ministry of Power).

10.1 Indian Railways Track Electrification and Further Expansion during 1925-1930:

In 1904, the idea to electrify the railway network was proposed by W.H. White, chief engineer of the then Bombay Presidency government. He proposed the electrification of the two Bombay-based companies, the Great Indian Peninsula Railway and the Bombay Baroda and Central India Railway, now known as CR and WR respectively. Bothe companies were in favour of the proposal. However, it took another year to obtain necessary permissions from the British Government and to upgrade the railway infrastructure in Bombay City. The Government of India appointed Mr. Merz as a consultant to give an opinion on the electrification of railways. But Mr. Merz resigned before making any concrete suggestions, except the replacement of the first Vasai Bridge on the BB&CI by a stronger one.

Moreover, as the project was in the process of being executed, the First World War broke out and put the brakes on the project. The First World War placed heavy strain on the railway infrastructure in India. Railway production in the country was diverted to meet the needs of British forces outside India. By the end of the war, Indian Railways were in a state of dilapidation and disrepair. By 1920, Mr. Merz formed a consultancy firm of his own a partner, Mr. Maclellan. The government retained his firm for the railway electrification project. Plans were drawn up for rolling stock and electric infrastructure for Bombay-Poona/Igatpuri/Vasai and Madras Tambaram routes. The secretary of state of India sanctioned these schemes in October 1920. All the impetus for the electrification, except power supply was imported from various companies in England. And similar to the running of the first ever railway train from Bombay to Thane on April 16, 1953, the first ever electric train in India also ran from Bombay. The debut journey, however, war a shorter one. The first electric train ran between Bombay Victoria Terminus and Kurla, a distance of 16 km, on February 3, 1925 along the city's harbor route and first ever railway budget was also presented in India (Accordingly Acworth Committee

report of 1921). And then various sections on the railway network were progressively electrified and commission during 1925 to 1930 and which are as follows:

- 1925: The first Railway Rail Budget was presented.
- 3 Feb. 1925: The first electric passenger train in India ran between Victoria Terminus and Kurla on 1,500 Volts DC overhead traction. Cammell Laird and Uerdingen wagon fabric manufactured the locomotives for this train. The Victoria Terminus to Bandra section was electrified, the Oudh and Rohil Khund Railway was merged with EIR, and the first Railway budget was presented in the same year.
- 1926: The Kurla to Kalyan section was electrified with 1,500 Volts DC. Electrification to Poona and Igatpuri over the Bhore and Thal Ghast was also completed, and the Chabagh Railway station in Lucknow was built that year.
- Jan. 1928: The Bandra to Virar section was electrified with 1,500 Volts DC.
- 1928: The Frontier Mail made its inaugural run between Bombay Victoria Terminus and Pashawar. The Country's first automatic color-light signals became operational, on Great Indian Peninsula Railway's (GIPR's) lines between Bombay Victoria Terminus and Byculla.
- 1928: The Kanpur Central and Lucknow stations opened. In this year the Grand Trunk Express began running between Peshawar and Mangalore, the Punjab Limited Express began running between Mumbai and Lahore, and automatic color-light signaling was extended to the Byculla-Kurla section.
- 1 June, 1930: The Deccan Queen began service with seven coaches on the Great Indian Peninsula Railway's (GIPR's) electrification route from Bombay Victoria Terminus to Poona. The Hyderabad Godavari Valley Railway was merged into Nizam's state Railway and the route of the Grand Trunk Express was changed to Delhi to Madras that year.

10.2 Electrification expansion of Railway Lines in the 2013-2017:

As per the Ministry of Railways report, during last four year (FY 2013-2017), total 103 Railway Electrification project consisting of 16,815 Route Kilo Meters (RKM) at estimated cost of Rs. 176.15 billion have been sanctioned and about 4,777 Route Kilo Meters (RKM) were electrified during the same period. Going ahead under "Mission Electrification" project, Indian Railway plans for electrification of 24,400 Route Kilo Meters (RKM) in the next five years which is almost equal to what has been done from introduction of electric traction since 3 February, 1925. The following table shows the electrification project in India:

Table 2: Indian Railway Electrification Lines

Indian Railway Electrification Lines	
Financial Year	Railway Electrification (RKM)
Financial Year 2011	740
Financial Year 2012	804
Financial Year 2013	937
Financial Year 2014	1033
Financial Year 2015	1089
Financial Year 2016	1190
Financial Year 2017	1465
Financial Year 2018 (T)	4000

Source: Central Organisation for Electrification, Budget Speech (2018)

11. Rail Tract Electrification of Assam the State of North East India:

During British rule, all links from the northern part of Bengal and Assam to the rest of India were through the eastern part of Bengal. The most important connection was the Calcutta–Parbatipur–Haldibari–Siliguri link first established in 1878 and then developed in stages. During the nineteenth century, Lalmonirhat was linked to the Dooars. In pre-independence days, a metre gauge line running via Radhikapur, Biral, Parbatipur, Tista, Gitaldaha and Golokganj connected Fakiragram in Assam with Katihar in Bihar. With the partition of India in 1947, all these links were lost. Indian Railways took up the Assam Link Project in 1948 to build a rail link between Fakiragram and Kishanganj. Fakiragram was connected to the Indian railway system in 1950 through the Indian portion of North Bengal with a metre gauge track. The New Jalpaiguri–New Bongaigaon section was partly new construction, partly old line converted to broad gauge in 1966. The 265 km (165 mi) long 1,676 mm (5 ft 6 in) wide broad gauge Siliguri-Jogihopa line was constructed between 1963 and 1965. The Haldibari–New Jalpaiguri line has gone through two successive gauge changes. As most other railway tracks in the area were metre gauge, the line was converted from broad gauge to metre gauge in 1949. Then in 1960s when broad gauge was introduced in the area, the line was converted back to broad gauge and connected to the new station at New Jalpaiguri. The metre gauge branch line from Malbazar in Jalpaiguri district to Changrabandha in Cooch Behar district is now an isolated section, with no service, as per the railway time table. In pre-independence days, the line was up to Mogalhat, now in Bangladesh. The present metre gauge line on the Bangladesh side from Burimari to Lalmonirhat is still functional. The Alipuduar–Bamanhat branch line ends near the India-Bangladesh border across the Dharla River. In pre-independence days, it used to connect to

Mogalhat, now in Bangladesh, across the Dharla. The bridge is broken. The line from Golokganj meets the branch line. The New Cooch Behar–Golokganj section is nearing conversion to broad gauge. The line passed through Gitaldaha at some point of time. The 66 km Fakiragram-Dhubri branch line was inaugurated after gauge conversion in September 2010.

Announcing a slew of steps for rapid and wide scale development of rail connectivity in the North Eastern Region, the Minister of Railways, Suresh Prabhakar announced a Rs. 5000 crore joint venture with State Government of Assam. To construct four elevated railway tracks between Kamakhya and New Guwahati to eliminate 12 level crossing gates in Guwahati city. The Minister made the announcement while laying foundation stone for the project of doubling of railway line from New Bongaigaon to Kamakhya via Goalpara Town and the doubling of railway line from Digaru to Hojai. He also laid much demanded Railway Electrification project for Raninagar Jalpaiguri-Guwahati via Rangiya railway line and flagged off the first passenger train services on the 10 km Karimganj-Maishashan newly converted broad gauge section in Barak valley of Assam.

Electrification of railway route from Katihar to Raninagar Jalpaiguri and from Maldah Town to Kumedpur sections had been in an advanced stage. The project for electrification from Raninagar Jalpaiguri to New Bongaigaon and then from New Bongaigaon to Guwahati was entrusted with Rail Vikash Nigam Limited , a Mini Ratna Public Sector Undertaking under Ministry of Railways, in 2014 and 2015 respectively in Assam. The Rail Vikash Nigam Limited will execute the project on turnkey basis. Under the project 382 route km and 687 track km of railway lines will be electrified. Electrification of railway lines in Assam had been a long standing demand of people of the state. It is also a long-term goal of Indian Railway to electrify all railway routes in the country to reduced carbon footprint and make railways greener. The Indian Railway under Mission electrification would make 90 percent of railway tracks in India electrified. Completion of the project will ensure that Guwahati will have a seamless electrified route to cities like Kolkata and New Delhi and eliminate the need for changing locomotives from electric to diesel and vice versa. This will also ensure reduction of journey time and possibility of increasing speed of trains. Northeast India being a richly endowed eco-sensitive zone, the measure for de-carbonization by railway electrification would be all the more relevant in ensuring a green future for the people of the region. Northeast Frontier Railway after taking a quantum leap by eliminating all unmanned level crossings has now embarked for complete railway track electrification till Guwahati targeted to be completed by 2020. Other branch lines like Coochbehar-Golokganj-Dhubri, Rangiya-Rangapara-Harmuti-Naharlagun, Chaparmukh-Silghat, Mariani-Furkating via Jorhat, and Tinsukia-Makum-Tirap have also received the required sanction for electrification.

NF Railway has started to electrify all its routes, to fulfill the ambitious project ‘Mission Electrification’ of Indian Railways successful. The high speed electric trains are to reach all Guwahati by 2020 and in the rest of the Northeast states by 2022 with the Northeast Frontier Railways (NFR) setting the same target. The works for the electrification traction is likely to give an impetus to passengers and goods movement in the Northeast where poor communications networks has always been a common complaint. The NFR work for electrification of the tracks has been divided among two agencies - Centre for Railway Electrification (CORE) and Rail Vikas Nigam Limited (RVNL). The RVNL has been entrusted with the electrification of the 382km Raninagar-Jalpaiguri to Guwahati via Rangiya portion. The CORE is working on electrification of the 267km tracks from Katihar to Raninagar-Jalpaiguri. "New Bongaigaon to Kamakhya via Goalpara (175km) and Guwahati to Dibrugarh via Lumding (661km) is being implemented by CORE. Contracts have already been awarded and work is in various stages of progress. Lumding to Badarpur (172km), Badarpur to Karimganj-Agartala-Sabroom-Akhaura including all branch lines to Silchar, Jiribam, Bhairabi, Dullabcherra, Mahishasan (590km) have also been sanctioned and will be implemented by CORE."

12. Summary of Findings on the Study

The main important points of findings of the study are follows:

- Electric lines means that trains with heavy diesel engines are not needed and the trains don't need to carry their own fuel and fuel is supplied through the overhead cable. Thus, this means the electric are the lighter than the diesel trains.
- It is benefits for the passengers that the journey in Electric trains will be faster and quieter journeys.
- It could connect stations to wider networks.
- There also a phenomenon called the sparks effect in which electrification leads to more people using the train.
- Electrifying rail links will support the vital tourism industry in the area, and help us building a stronger economy.
- Better acceleration in electric trains could mean shorter journey times and smoother than diesel.
- Diesel fuel is also significantly more expensive than electric traction.
- With electricity being increasingly generated by renewable, the carbon footprint of electric trains is being reduced accordingly.

- Electric traction also eliminates harmful diesel engine emissions and particulates which are a particular issue at stations.
- Electrification will lead to significant benefits in the areas of safety, capacity, speed, energy security and sustainability in the railways.
- It is great advantages of electric tractions are pollution free atmosphere not only to the travelers but also to the surrounding environment. Electric traction is proven to be less pollutant than the existing diesel mode and thus could be more eco-friendly to an area having delicate flora and fauna. Electric traction could reduce noise and air pollution and result I lesser disturbance to wild life habitant of the region.

13. Conclusion:

Electric traction is a more environment friendly option. By using electric traction over diesel traction, the nation reduces the use of fossil fuel, reduces import of petroleum and reduces its carbon footprints. For Indian Railways, electrification is cheaper source of energy and electric rolling stock is also capable of regeneration process. The use of rail electrification increase in speed, ease of operation and better economic viability of the operations are the main positive aspects of using electric traction. Over the years, Indian Railway has undertaken the work of electrification of various routes or section. The Traffic congestion, accidents and air pollution are serious problems in India. Traffic management schemes, efficient pricing policies, and emission controls on road vehicles are effective instruments for reducing congestion and air pollution of road transport. Electrification of railways has many advantages for both the operator and society. And electrified rail system can have a number of operational and environmental benefits. In terms of operational aspects, it facilitates the use of high-speed, high-powered, high-acceleration and lower-noise traction motors in comparison with diesel engines. These factors contribute to an improved of customer service and help to improve competitiveness with other modes of transport. On the other hand, electrification helps in reducing the external costs of road vehicles through possible switching between the two modes. Then on social grounds, there will be a number of societal benefits for electrification schemes.

It is well acknowledged that the economic and human potential of India's North Eastern Region is severely contained due to its transport infrastructure deficiency. The Central and State Governments are now jointly focused to build infrastructure in the North Eastern Region. Indian Railways has been the prime mover of the nation and has the distinction of the being the largest railways system in Asia and the second largest railway system in the World under single management. The world is looking to engage with the emerging economic hotspot the East and it is in the North-East India that South East Asia begins. Most urgent and strategic interventions are required for the North Eastern Region to play the arrowhead role for India. The transport infrastructure will be vital to strengthen integration with the region and with the rest of the country, and also for India's increased integration with the South East. Improving connectivity shall have to be foremost priority for social and economic mobility and market integration. The greater connectivity and economic integration of India's North East with its Eastern neighbours is to be considering a key focus area for growth and development of the region. The country worked with the vision that India's growth story will pick up speedier only when the Northeast Region developed at the same pace in a balance manner. The progress of the North Eastern Region will be able to lead vast section of population towards prosperity. Indian Railways has staged a dramatic turnaround in recent year.

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